

InterContinental Hotels Group

I-Intern Program

This certificate is awarded to

Sayan Ali Khan

Student of **Srinivas University College of Hotel Management & Tourism - Mangaluru**

For successfully completing Industrial Training

At **Holiday Inn Chandigarh Panchkula**

From 09th December, 2021 to 14th April, 2022 with 91 % Attendance

Overall Performance Rating: [Good]

“All of you” at IHG

Anurag Bharadwaj
Holiday Inn Chandigarh Panchkula

IHG[®]

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HOTELS & RESORTS

KIMPTON[®]
HOTELS & RESTAURANTS

HUALUXE
HOTELS AND RESORTS
華邑酒店及度假村[®]

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Holiday Inn

H
Holiday Inn
Express

STAYBRIDGE
SUITES

hotel
INDIGO

EMEN
HOTELS

CROWNE PLAZA[®]
HOTELS & RESORTS

H
Holiday Inn
Club
Vacations

H
Holiday Inn
Resort

CANDLEWOOD
SUITES

IHG[®] Rewards
Club[®]

*IHG[®] Rewards Club not applicable to Kimpton[®] Hotels & Restaurants; to be included at a future date.